

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

VALIDATION OF A FORCED DEGRADATION UPLC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF BECLOMETHASONE DIPROPIONATE IN RESPULES DOSAGE FORM

Anas Rasheed^{*1}, Dr. Osman Ahmed²

¹Research Scholar, Faculty of Pharmacy, Pacific Academy of Higher Education and Research University, Udaipur.

²Research Supervisor, Faculty of Pharmacy, Pacific Academy of Higher Education and Research University, Udaipur.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 03/05/2017

Available online
31/05/2017

Keywords

Beclomethasone Dipropionate,
UPLC,
Validation,
Forced Degradation Method.

ABSTRACT

Respules are the drugs in aqueous suspension form contained and packed in respiratory ampules, they are administered through inhalation by a device called nebulizer. The purpose of the study is to validate an UPLC method for forced degradation studies of respules which may be useful in quality control of the respiratory drugs in production for human consumption. A specific, precise, accurate and forced degradation UPLC method is validated for estimation of beclomethasone dipropionate in aqueous suspension for nebulizer. The method employed, with Hypersil BDS C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m) column in an gradient mode, with mobile phase of Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v. The flow rate was 0.1 ml/min and effluent was monitored at 239 nm. Retention time was found to be 3.453 \pm 0.08 min. The method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ) etc. in accordance with ICH guidelines. Linear regression analysis data for the calibration plot showed that there was good linear relationship between response and concentration in the range of 1- 10 μ g/ml respectively. The LOD and LOQ values for were found to be 0.31607(μ g/ml) and 0.95781(μ g/ml) respectively. No chromatographic interference from respule's excipients and degradants were found. The proposed method was successfully used for estimation of beclomethasone dipropionate in aqueous suspension for nebulizer (respules form).

Corresponding author

Anas Rasheed

Research Scholar,
Faculty of Pharmacy,
Pacific Academy of Higher Education and Research University, Udaipur.
anasrasheed6500@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Anas Rasheed** et al. Validation of a Forced Degradation UPLC Method for Estimation of Beclomethasone Dipropionate in Respules Dosage Form. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(05).

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Beclomethasone dipropionate, 9-chloro-11 β -Hydroxy-16 β -methylpregna-1,4-diene-3,20-dione 17,21-dipropionate (Fig. 1), is a glucocorticoid used as first-line, anti-inflammatory therapy to treatment of all asthmatic patients in the form of respules, pressurized inhalation.^[1,2]

Chemical stability of Beclomethasone dipropionate is a matter of great concern as it affects the safety and efficacy of the finished drug product. Forced degradation studies provide data to support identification of possible degradants; degradation pathways and intrinsic stability of the Beclomethasone dipropionate molecule and validation of stability indicating analytical procedures.^[4,5,6]

A detailed literature revealed that several analytical methods have been reported for the determination of Beclomethasone Dipropionate in pharmaceutical pressurized inhalation dosage forms. In our present knowledge, there is no method reported for the estimation forced degradation studies of Beclomethasone Dipropionate in pharmaceutical pressurized inhalation dosage form by UPLC.^[13-17]

Hence, the aim was to develop a specific, rapid, sensitive, and accurate UPLC method which can estimate the forced degradation studies of Beclomethasone Dipropionate.

The present work aims with the developed method to be only this mobile phase is sufficient for quantification of degraded products under stress.

Every form of drug produced or developed must be assured of good quality of standard API and Finished product, respules are a different kind of drug dosage form so it should be measured for its standard quality and assured for a good organic chemical compound having better chemical effects with both appropriate and inappropriate impurities.

The purpose of the study is to acquire quality control data and to monitor the behaviour of respules in forced degradation studies by studying the respules quality control analysis may be useful for better standard of respules's production and good quality of drug in inhalation form.

Fig.1: Molecular Structure of Beclomethasone dipropionate, 9-chloro-11 β -Hydroxy-16 β -methylpregna-1,4-diene-3,20-dione 17,21-dipropionate^[12]

EXPERIMENTAL:

MATERIALS:

Beclomethasone dipropionate (99.99 % purity) used as analytical standard was procured from Active Pharma Labs (Hyderabad).

HPLC grade methanol, Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was purchased from Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India. Distilled, 0.45 μ m filtered water used for UPLC quantification and preparation of buffer. Buffers and all other chemicals were analytical grade. The aqueous suspension for nebulizer (Beclate Inhaler 200Md) labeled to contain 250 mcg /actuation of Beclomethasone dipropionate All chemicals used were of pharmaceutical or special analytical grade.

INSTRUMENTATION:

Acquity, Waters UPLC system consisting of a Water 2695 binary gradient pump, an inbuilt auto sampler, a column oven and Water 2996 wavelength absorbance detector (PDA) was employed throughout the analysis.

The data was collected using Empower 2 software. The column used was Hypersil BDS C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m). A Band line sonorex sonicator was used for enhancing dissolution of the compounds. A Labindia pH System 362 was used for pH adjustment.

Chromatographic Conditions:**Table 1: Chromatographic Conditions of the validating method.**

Parameter	Value
Column	Hypersil BDS C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v
Flow rate	0.1 mL/min
Run time	12 Min.
Column Temperature	Maintained at ambient temperature
Injection volume	20 μ L
Detection wavelength	239nm
Diluent	Mobile Phase

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:**Preparation of Diluent:**

In order to achieve the separation under the optimized conditions after experimental trials that can be summarized. Stationary phase like Hypersil BDS C18 (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m) column was most suitable one, since it produced symmetrical peaks with high resolution and a very good sensitivity and with good resolution. The flow rate was maintained 0.1mL min⁻¹ shows good resolution. The PDA detector response of Beclomethasone dipropionate was studied and the best wavelength was found to be 239 nm showing highest sensitivity.

The mixture of three solutions methanol, 0.1% orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v. The buffer used is 2.96 gms of Sodium phosphate in 100 ml with gradient programming was used as mobile phase at 0.1 mL/min was found to be an appropriate mobile phase for separation of Beclomethasone Dipropionate. The column was maintained at ambient temperature.

Preparation of internal standard solution: (Sol 1)

Weighed accurately about 100 mg of Testosterone propionate working standard and transfer to 1000 ml volumetric flask, add 100 ml Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and then dilute to 1000 ml with diluent. 10 ml of the above solution to 100 ml with diluent and filter out above solution through the 0.45micron filter. (10 μ g/ml Concentration).

Preparation of Beclomethasone dipropionate standard solution:(Sol 2)

Weighed accurately about 100 mg of Beclomethasone dipropionate and transfer to 1000 ml volumetric flask, add 100 ml Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and then dilute to 1000 ml with diluent.

Preparation of Mixed Standard solution

Pipette out 10 ml of (solution 1) and (solution 2) in to 100 ml volumetric flask, dilute to volume with diluent and mix.

Preparation of Sample solution

Perform the priming of first three sprays of the pump in the air for wastage, then weigh 1000 ml dry volumetric flask and actuate spray 10 times into 1000 ml volumetric flask and weigh accurately the sample quantity for calculation (equivalent 500 mcg Beclomethasone dipropionate) add 80 ml diluent and sonicate for 10 minutes, cool to room temperature and diluent to make up 1000 ml. Transfer 100 ml above solution and 300 ml of (solution 1) into 500 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with diluents. Filter the solution through 0.45 μ .filter (concentration of Beclomethasone dipropionate 10 mcg/ml).

Forced Degradation Studies

Forced degradation studies like acid hydrolysis, basic hydrolysis, dry heat degradation, wet heat degradation and oxidative degradation were carried out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Validation

The analytical method was validated with respect to parameters such as linearity, precision, specificity and accuracy, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantitation (LOQ) and robustness in compliance with ICH guidelines.

Fig. 2: Standard Chromatogram of Beclomethasone dipropionate, using mobile phase of Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 % v/v/v.

Linearity and Range:

The linearity of an analytical procedure is the ability to obtain test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of an analyte in the sample.

The calibration curve showed good linearity in the range of 1 – 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, for Beclomethasone dipropionate (API) with correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.9996. A typical calibration curve has the regression equation of $y = 51046.38x + 4603.667$ for Beclomethasone dipropionate. Results are given in Table 3.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):

The LOD and LOQ were calculated by mathematical equation. $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{standard deviation} \div \text{slope}$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{standard deviation} \div \text{slope}$. The LOD of Beclomethasone dipropionate was found to be 0.31607 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) and the LOQ of Beclomethasone dipropionate was found to be 0.95781 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$). Results are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of validation parameters for the proposed method.

PARAMETER	Beclomethasone dipropionate
Linearity	1 – 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Intercept (c)	4603.667
Slope (m)	51046.38
Correlation coefficient	0.9996
LOD	0.31607 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
LOQ	0.95781 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Precision:

The Precision of the method was studied in terms of intraday and interday precision of sample injections (5µg/ml). Intraday precision was investigated by injecting six replicate samples of each of the sample on the same day. The % RSD was found to be 0.534. Interday precision was assessed by analysis of the 6 solutions on three consecutive days. The % RSD obtained was found to be 0.925. Low % RSD values indicate that the method is precise. The results are given in table 4.

Table: 4, Results of Precision Studies.

Beclomethasone dipropionate			
Precision Studies			
Parameter	Peak Area	% RSD	%LC
Intraday precision	512738		99.98%
	512619	0.02%	99.99%
	512803		99.99%
Inter day precision	513583		100.14%
	513691	0.02%	100.16%
	513830		100.19%
Instrument:1 Acquity UPLC Waters,2695H	512637		99.96%
	512764	0.03%	99.98%
Instrument:2 Agilent Technologies,1290	512906		100.01%
	512639		99.96%
	512772	0.03%	99.98%
	512908		100.01%
Average			100.02
Std.Dev			0.083
%RSD			0.08%

Robustness:

Small deliberate changes in chromatographic conditions such as change in temperature ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), flow rate ($\pm 0.1\text{ml/min}$) and wavelength of detection ($\pm 2\text{nm}$) were studied to determine the robustness of the method. The results were in favor of (% RSD < 2%) the developed UPLC method for the analysis of Beclomethasone dipropionate. The results are given in table 5.

Table: 5, Results of Robustness Studies.

Robustness Studies			
Parameter	Value	Peak Area	% RSD
Flow Rate	Low	512939	
	Actual	513272	
	Plus	513508	0.06%
Temperature	Low	512948	
	Actual	513265	0.06%
	Plus	513523	
Wavelength	Low	512604	
	Actual	513442	0.13%
	Plus	513897	

Accuracy:

To study the accuracy of method, recovery studies were carried out by spiking of standard drug solution to pre-analyzed sample at three different levels i.e., at 50, 100, and 150%. The resultant solutions were then reanalyzed by the proposed method. At each level of the amount, six determinations were performed. From the data obtained, the method was found to be accurate. The % recovery and %RSD were calculated and presented in Table 6.

Tale: 6, Results of accuracy study.

Beclomethasone dipropionate						
Level %	Amount Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery (%)	Std.Dev	% RSD
50	16.51	16.29	98.66			
100	33.03	32.88	99.54	98.90	0.552	0.56%
150	49.54	48.81	98.52			

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES

According to Singh and Bakshi, the stress testing suggests a target degradation of 20-80 % for establishing stability indicating nature of the method. UPLC study of samples obtained on stress testing of Beclomethasone dipropionate under different conditions using mixture Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v as a mobile solvent system suggested the following degradation behavior.

Acid hydrolysis:

An accurate 10 ml of pure drug sample solution was transferred to a clean and dry round bottom flask (RBF). 30 ml of 0.1 N HCl was added to it. It was refluxed in a water bath at 60°C for 4 hours. Drug became soluble after reflux which was insoluble initially. Allowed to cool at room temperature. The sample was then neutralized using 2N NaOH solution and final volume of the sample was made up to 100ml with water to prepare 100ppm solution. It was injected into the UPLC system against a blank of Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v after optimizing the mobile phase composition, chromatogram was recorded and shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Chromatogram showing the degraded products in Acidic degradation.

Basic hydrolysis:

An accurate 10 ml of pure drug sample solution was transferred to a clean and dry RBF. 30 ml of 0.1N NaOH was added to it. It was refluxed in a water bath at 60°C for 4 hours. Drug became soluble after reflux which was insoluble initially. It was allowed to cool at room temperature. The sample was then neutralized using 2N HCl solution and final volume of the sample was made up to 100ml with water to prepare 100ppm solution. It was injected into the UPLC system against a blank of Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 %v/v/v after optimizing the mobile phase composition, chromatogram was recorded and shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Chromatogram showing the degraded products in Basic degradation.

Wet heat degradation:

Accurate 10 ml of pure drug sample was transferred to a clean and dry RBF. 30 ml of HPLC grade water was added to it. Then, it was refluxed in a water bath at 60°C for 6 hours uninterruptedly. After the completion of reflux, the drug became soluble and the mixture of drug and water was allowed to cool at room temperature. Final volume was made up to 100 ml with HPLC grade water to prepare 100 ppm solution. It was injected into the UPLC system against a blank of Methanol, 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 45:35:20 % v/v/v after optimizing the mobile phase composition, chromatogram was recorded and shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Chromatogram showing the degraded products in Wet heat degradation.

Oxidation with (3%) H₂O₂:

Approximately 10 ml of pure drug sample was transferred in a clean and dry 100 ml volumetric flask. 30 ml of 3% H₂O₂ and a little methanol was added to it to make it soluble and then kept as such in dark for 24 hours. Final volume was made up to 100 ml using water to prepare 100 ppm solution. The above sample was injected into the UPLC system. The chromatogram was recorded and shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Chromatogram showing the degraded products in H₂O₂.

In all degradation studies, there was a significant formation of degradation products when compared to that of a standard. This indicates that, the drug may be degraded to low molecular weight non-chromophoric compounds.

Table:7, Forced Degradation study for the developed method.

Nature of Stress	Degradation condition	Time(h)	Number of degradation products (Rt)
Acidic	60°C	3	3 (0.512, 1.313, 1.878)
Basic	60°C	9	1 (2.921)
Oxidative	RT	48	1 (1.128)
Wet Heat	105°C	24	2 (4.192, 4.783, 5.011)

CONCLUSION

A specific, sensitive and selective forced degradation UPLC method has been validated for the analysis of Beclomethasone dipropionate in bulk drug and respule dosage form. Based on peak purity results, obtained from the analysis of force degradation samples using described method, it can be concluded that the absence of co-eluting peak along with the main peak of Beclomethasone dipropionate indicated that the developed method is specific for the estimation of Beclomethasone dipropionate in presence of degradation products. Further the proposed UPLC method has excellent precision, sensitivity and reproducibility. Even though no attempt has been made to identify the degraded products, proposed method can be used as forced degradation method for assay of Beclomethasone dipropionate in commercial formulations. The authors recommend future research for Beclomethasone dipropionate in respules dosage form.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to Active Pharma Labs (Hyderabad, India) for providing gift sample of Beclomethasone dipropionate.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

UPLC – Ultra Pressure Liquid Chromatography
 API – Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
 LOD – Limit Of Detection
 LOQ – Limit Of Quantification
 mcg – microgram
 mL – milli Litre

REFERENCES

1. Beclomethasone Dipropionate. The American Society of Health-System Pharmacists. Retrieved Dec 2, 2015.
2. Hamilton, Richart (2015). Tarascon Pocket Pharmacopoeia 2015 Deluxe Lab-Coat Edition. Jones & Bartlett Learning. p. 451. ISBN 9781284057560.
1. 3.Sangita B. Gavitre*, Dr. Ashok P. Pingle, Nanasaheb R. Kale, Javed A. Mirza., RP-HPLC Assay Method Development and Validation of Beclomethasone Dipropionate in Metered Dose Inhaler- A Research; World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences; Volume 3, Issue 8, 2193-2206.
3. M Blessy, , Ruchi D. Patel, Prajesh N. Prajapati, Y.K. Agrawal; Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs—A review; Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis; Volume 4, Issue 3, June 2014, Pages 159–165.
4. S. Singh and M. Bakshi. Guidance on conduct of stress tests to determine inherent stability of drugs. Pharm. Technol. 2000; 26: 24–31.

5. ICH guidelines, Q1A (R2): Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products (revision 2), International Conference on Harmonization. Available from:(<http://www.fda.gov/downloads/RegulatoryInformation/Guidances/ucm128204.pdf>), 2003.
6. USP-NF; Validation of Compendial Procedures; General Chapters; Vol.1;2010: 734-736.
7. Fifield .F W.; Kealey D.; Principal and practice of analytical chemistry; USA Blackwell publishing; 5th edition, 2004: 2,5-7.
8. Dudhasia K.R.; Patel A.V.; Patel C.N.; Development and Validation of a Reversed phase HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Clotrimazole and Beclomethasone dipropionate in lotion and cream dosage form; Journal of Chronicle of Young Scientist;2014;(3):1-107.
9. Reddy U.M.; Reddy K.H.; BObbarala V.; Penumajji., Determination of Beclomethasone Dipropionate, Clotrimazole, Chloramphenicol, Lidocaine, in Pharmaceutical Formulations using a novel RP-HPLC method. International Journal Of Pharma and Biosciences;vol-2:2011:(3): 453-462.
10. Prajapati N. B.; Dey S.S.; Dr. Upadhyay U.M.; Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous estimation of Salicylic acid and Beclomethasone dipropionate in their Bulk and Combined Dosage form;International journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development; 2013;5(3):1-50.
11. David A. Williams, William O. Foye, Thomas L. Lemke; Foye's principles of medicinal chemistry; 6th Ed (2008) Wolters Kluwer Health; 698-728.
12. B. Srivastava , B. K. Sharma, Uttam Singh Baghel , Yashwant , NehaSethi. Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC): A Chromatographic Technique.Int. J. Pharm. Quality Assurance.2010; 2(1): 19-25.
13. Nguyen D.T., Guillaume D, Rudaz S, Veuthey J. L., Fast Analysis In Liquid Chromatography Using Small Particle Size And High Pressure. J Sep Sci. 2006 Aug;29(12):1836-48.
14. Katharina Sterz, Gerhard Scherer, Josef Ecker. A Simple And Robust UPLC-SRM/MS Method To Quantify Urinary Eicosanoids.J Lipid Res.2013:1-28.
15. Ashok kumar, UPLC: A preeminent technique in pharmaceutical analysis. Acta poloniae pharmaceutica– drug research. 69(30), 2012, 371-380.
16. Michael E Swartz, Ultra performance liquid chromatography UPLC: an introduction. Separation science redefined.1:2005;8-14.

54878478451170504

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

